

SERSCIDA project Training Activities

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SEEDS Kick-off meeting, Lausanne, 4. - 6. May 2015

Training delivered was a mixture of:

- Ongoing external training events
 - (CESSDA Trust workshop and the CESSDA expert seminar and participation at the 2013 IASSIST conference and the first regional meeting of the Data without Boundaries project)
- Internal tailor-made training content

Design of training activities

1. Establishing training needs (information about existing interests and know how, who are the target users)
2. First draft of a national roadmap of data service establishment (meeting at ADP in May 2013)
3. UK Data Archive provided a bespoke version of its well-established course, 'How to set up and run a data service'.
4. Data Service Training Manual produced with links to the policy documents, deposit forms and licences used in established organisations
5. Training event preparing and depositing a dataset for use by the social science research community at ADP.
6. face to face meetings/visits for policy makers, potential funders and stakeholders of the new services to provide an overview of how data services are structured, funded and governed in a variety of countries (UK, Slovenia and Sweden)

Questions for considerations of SEEDS training activities

- Feed back assessment from SERSCIDA WB partners – what proved useful, where there are additional needs
- What external training is ongoing, whom it address, what is missing (CESSDA, FOSTER, IASSIST)
- Assessment of new partners training needs
- Competencies overview among partners and external experts for delivering training on specified topic